

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ADVANCED TECHNIQUES FOR MONITORING DETONATION CHARACTERISTICS OF HYDROCARBON FUELS

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Abstract

In recent years, the quality and utilization of motor gasoline have become increasingly critical, influencing both technological advancements and economic growth. With the rising demands for enhanced motor gasoline performance, there is a pressing need for innovative types that offer superior characteristics. One of the primary requirements for motor gasoline is optimal knock resistance, ensuring smooth engine operation across various modes.

This study explores the rapid assessment of the detonation properties of motor fuels through advanced physico-chemical methods that monitor the chemical reactions and associated physical phenomena of these fuels. A novel approach discussed in this article involves the cold-flame combustion method, utilizing an oxidation reaction with oxygen-enriched gases. This method includes measuring specific physical effects correlated with fuel detonation properties. The introduction of ozone, a potent oxidizing agent and an allotrope of oxygen, presents new opportunities for enhancing the quality control of hydrocarbon fuels.

Focusing on product quality improvement and increased efficiency, this research investigates a method that incorporates ozone derived from the ambient air. The development and application of this method could significantly impact the refinement of hydrocarbon fuels, making the study of such innovative techniques pertinent and timely.

Keywords: motor gasoline, knock resistance, detonation properties, physico-chemical methods, cold-flame combustion, ozone oxidation, hydrocarbon fuel quality control, innovative techniques.

INTRODUCTION

The modern problems of Azerbaijan put forward the issues of rational use of oil raw materials, which serve as the basis for the further development of targeted petroleum products, the bulk of which are motor fuels, in the first place. The production of fuels, in particular gasolines, is a complex technological process and its coordinated functioning requires the possibility of prompt intervention - to change the quantities and ratios of the produced products.

The very intervention becomes possible if there is primary information about the current values of the controlled parameters of technological processes. The use of automatic analyzers of the composition and quality of substances in industrial production management systems can increase efficiency by eliminating or reducing laboratory tests, obtaining real-time information, and using intelligent systems that control production.

The main indicator of the quality of hydrocarbon fuels is knock resistance. Detonation is a special type of combustion of the working mixture, characterized by a high flame front propagation velocity and high local pressures. Detonation leads to overheating of the engine, incomplete combustion of fuel and is accompanied by smoky exhaust, causes unstable operation of the engine, a decrease in its power and efficiency. A measure of the knock resistance of fuels is the "octane number" (ON). The octane number is an indicator of the detonation resistance of the fuel, numerically equal to the percentage of isooctane in the same mixture with n-heptane, which is equivalent to the test fuel in terms of detonation intensity in the cylinder of a special single-cylinder engine under standard test conditions. Two

individual hydrocarbons are used as reference fuels: isooctane (2,2,4-trimethylpentane C_8H_{18}) and n-heptane ($n-C_7H_{16}$), which have similar physicochemical properties, but differ sharply in detonation resistance. The detonation resistance of isooctane is conventionally taken as 100 units, and n-heptane as 0.

According to the measurement methods, the existing methods for determining the ON of motor fuels can be divided into two groups: octane meters that implement the direct method of measurement and octane meters, which are based on indirect measurement methods.

Octane meters that implement the direct method of measurement are made mainly on the basis of standard test engines [1]. The practical implementation of this method takes quite a long time (1.5-3 hours), which completely excludes the possibility of their use for operational control of technological processes.

An example of the second type are alternative methods, such as the cold flame oxidation (CFO) method, in which the fuel is oxidized by ambient air. In this case, the dependences of the detonation resistance on the dielectric constant, the absorption spectrum, and also the overpressure in cold flame oxidation reactors (CFOR) are most often used [2]. In this case, one of the physical effects accompanying the chemical reaction is measured, and the magnitude of this effect is proportional to the value of the ON of the fuel under study.

An analysis of the CFO method made it possible to conclude that the reaction itself was insufficiently intense, which is associated with the low chemical activity of the oxidizing agent, molecular oxygen, which is present in the ambient air. It is impossible to increase the amount of oxygen by increasing the air flow

through the reaction chamber without removing the gaseous test fuel from this chamber. A technical contradiction arises - on the one hand, the amount of air should not change - on the other hand, it should contain more oxidizer.

An analysis of the situation led to a solution to the contradiction: to increase the reactivity of air by converting it into a more chemically aggressive form of an oxidizing agent, namely, into the form of ozone (O_3). Ozone, in addition to its high reactivity, is also distinguished by the fact that it can be easily obtained from the ambient air by the barrier discharge method, moreover, at minimal energy costs and in quantities sufficient for analytical studies.

Temperature measurement during the interaction of ozone with fuel can be used for express determination of detonation properties of motor fuels.

EXPERIMENTS AND THEIR RESULTS

Studies of the possibilities of determining the detonation properties of hydrocarbon fuels were carried out on a stand, the schematic diagram of which is shown in Fig.1.

The stand consists of the following components:

- I - Gas preparation panel;
- II - ozonator;
- III - thermostat;
- IV - signal registration system;
- V - thermostat control system;
- VI - detector power supply system;
- VII - ozonator power supply system.

Fig.1. Scheme of the experimental stand

I – gas preparation panel; II - ozonator; III - thermostat; IV - signal registration system; V - thermostat control system; VI – detector power supply system; VII - power supply system of the ozonator; 1 - sample injection device; 2 – hollow column; 3 - detector; A - air; B - is ozone; C – analyzed substance; D - exhaust gases.

The gas preparation panel I serves to stabilize and control the gas flow A entering the investigated detector and ozonator. The studies were carried out using a pulse input of the dose of analyzed substances, according to which the dose of the substance through the sample injection device entered the hollow column 2, through which the carrier gas (air) flows with a constant volume flow. The hollow column serves to create a small time interval between the moment the sample is injected and the moment it enters the primary measuring transducer (PMT). This time is necessary to complete the transients associated with the injection of sample C through the inlet 1 into the carrier gas stream A.

The ozonator II is used for the synthesis of ozone from molecular oxygen supplied to it with a supply air flow A. The ozone synthesizer is a hermetic glass chamber that separates the inner and outer electrodes, between which an electrical breakdown and a discharge

occurs, passing through which, molecular oxygen located in the composition of the pumped air is converted into ozone.

Thermostat III serves to stabilize the temperature of the detector 3 and the gas flows entering it.

The IV-th signal registration system is designed to capture the information signal coming from the detector into a graphical signal that is convenient for subsequent interpretation.

The thermostat V control system is designed to create and maintain the required temperature regime in various parts of the thermostat III - in the area of the hollow column 2 and in the area immediately adjacent to the detector wall 3.

The power supply system of the ozonator VI is designed to create, regardless of the flow rate of the air supplying the ozonizer, the ozone concentration necessary for research.

A thermochemical ozonolysis detector is installed as a detector (Fig.2), which is a flow chamber 8 made of stainless steel, into the central through channel of which the channels for supplying ozone-containing gas and carrier gas through fitting 7 cut at a right angle. From one end of the flow chamber 8, an assembly 2 - 6 of the heating element is inserted and fixed with a pressure sleeve 1. The latter is a supporting metal foot 2, through which a ceramic insulator 3 passes into the cavity of the flow chamber of the body 8 (hereinafter referred to as the reaction chamber), having four through holes in its body. Rigid holders 6 of nichrome wire are passed through two of them, serving as a hot body 5. The same holders, brought out through the ceramic insulator 3, serve as electrical contacts for connecting electrical power.

Through the other two holes of the ceramic insulator 3, the wires of the CK TEK 4 are passed, the hot junction of which is attached to the surface of the nichrome wire 5, and the cold ends are brought out of the

analytical block. To the other end of the reaction chamber 8 is connected with a fitting 9 pneumopipe for discharge of exhaust gases.

During the study, the analyzed substance in the composition of the carrier gas enters the reaction chamber 8. The flow of ozone-containing gas also enters here. Gases, mixing with each other and moving along the hot body 5, enter into an almost instantaneous reaction, the intensity of which is determined by the degree of heat of the body 5. The hot junction of TEK 4, located on the surface of this body, serves not only to determine its temperature, but also to measure the amount of heat generated as a result of a chemical reaction and convert it into an electrical signal of measurement information. The graphic fixation of the latter occurs by registering the IV signal (Fig. 1). If a computer program is available, the measurement information is processed by a computer.

Fig.2. Design of the OOTM detector

1 - bushing; 2- metal heel; 3- ceramic insulator; 4 - TEK; 5 - hot body; 6 - holder; 7, 9 - fitting; 8 - reaction chamber.

Individual hydrocarbons in the gas phase were used as analyzed substances: ethylene, propylene; in the liquid phase: pentane, hexane, n-heptane, octane, nonane, decane, isooctane, cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, as well as certified gasolines of the oil refinery named after Heydar Aliyev.

At the beginning, the following gases were studied: olefins (ethylene and propylene), paraffins (propane-butane fraction), aromatic hydrocarbon (benzene). The doses were 0.1 cm^3 . The hollow column was not heated at the same time.

The results are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen from the graph that ozone reacts with all gases representing various homologous series of hydrocarbons, namely: olefins, paraffins, aromatics. The peak rise of propylene begins to grow at a temperature of 60°C , and for ethylene, which has a reaction rate much lower than that of propylene [3], from a temperature of 120°C . Later, from $\sim 240^\circ\text{C}$, the propane-butane fraction and benzene begin to manifest themselves. In the range of $400\text{-}500^\circ\text{C}$, the signals reach their maximum, after which they begin to fall.

Fig.3. Ozone reaction detector signals with various hydrocarbons with a cold wall of the reaction chamber

Next, the optimal flow rates of ozone-containing gas and carrier gas were determined. The optimal gas flow rates are taken to be 2 l/h for ozone and 1/h for the carrier gas (Fig. 4). The correspondence of the heating of the inner wall of the detector to the temperature of the hot body was also established.

Then an experiment was carried out, involving simultaneously the presence of all three components of the system: a hot body, ozone and the substance under

study. The results of this experiment are presented in fig. 5.

As follows from the figure, the signals of the vast majority of substances introduced for analysis begin at 220°C. The maximum of the signals falls on the temperature range of 550-600°C. The detector sensitivity in the region of 375°C, where the signals of each of the hydrocarbons were clearly separated, is, according to Figure 0, 4mV/% vol. (for n-heptane).

Fig. 4. Detector signals depending on flow rates ozone-containing gas and carrier gas

Fig.5. Detector signals using hot body, ozone and test substances

The next cycle of experiments was devoted to the study of pure substances with certain ON values: n-heptane (ON=0), hexane (25), pentane (66), cyclohexane (87), isooctane (100), benzene (106) [4]. As can be seen from fig. 6, almost all of these substances fell into the range of numbers (abscissa axis) characterizing the values of their ON.

Due to the fact that in the industry, when certifying motor fuels for their detonation resistance, it is customary to use n-heptane and isooctane as pure substances, calibration mixtures of n-heptane and isooctane were compiled in the ratios: 100/0, 80/20, 50 /50, 60/40, 20/80 and 0/100 (in % vol.). The results are shown in Fig.7.

Fig.6. Detector signal depending on pure hydrocarbons, having a standard value of ON

And, finally, the final experiment was a generalization of the study of gasoline samples obtained at different times at the refinery named after. G.Aliyeva. The

graph (Fig. 8) shows small deviations obtained as a result of repeated studies of these fuels for the value of their ON.

Fig.7. Detector responses to the introduction of reference mixtures into it

Fig.8. Results of experiments to determine the octane value of motor fuels

○- ON motor method

●- ON OOTM way

It should be noted that the graph is plotted in dimensionless units (ordinate-axis). The latter is due to the fact that in the course of the research it was noted that the signals of substances were observed to increase in their absolute values. At the same time, the ratio between the signals of different substances was preserved. At the end of the experiments, the nature of the fall of signals in time was investigated. The drop in signals is explained not by the drop in the physicochemical properties of the calibration mixtures, but by the uneven, in

time, drop in the catalytic activity of the hot body as a result of its coking. This is precisely what explains the high percentage of error found in the course of comparing the results obtained by the OOTM method with the results of tests by the standard method.

Numerical data are given in table 2, on the basis of which the results of studies of the values of the octane number of the OOTM method can be considered satisfactory.

Table 1

Test results of the OOTM method

№№ шт	ON motor method	ON OOTM way	Absolute error	Relative error
1	51	52	2,0	2,0
2	70	68	2,0	2,9
3	75	76	1,0	1,3
4	80	79,4	0,6	0,75
5	85	84,5	0,5	0,6
6	91	89,6	1,4	1,5
7	94	93	1,0	1,1
8	96	98	2,0	2,0

CONCLUSION

Theoretical and experimental studies led to the following conclusions:

- in the presence of a thermal field, the reaction with ozone extends to all homologous series of hydrocarbons;

- the reaction of ozone with hydrocarbons occurs with the release of an additional amount of heat;

- experimentally confirmed the possibility of implementing an operational method for determining the detonation properties of hydrocarbon fuels, called ozone-oxidizing thermochemical (OOTM), which involves mixing the vapors of the analyzed fuel with ozone in the presence of a hot body, as well as measuring the temperature increase at the time of the reaction and its correlation with the detonation properties of reference mixtures;

- a promising direction is the development and creation of intelligent systems for determining the detonation properties of hydrocarbon fuels using cold-flame ozone oxidation reactors.

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